

ON THE DIVISOR PRODUCTS AND PROPER DIVISOR PRODUCTS SEQUENCES*

LIU HONGYAN AND ZHANG WENPENG

Department of Mathematics, Northwest University
Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

ABSTRACT. Let n be a positive integer, $p_d(n)$ denotes the product of all positive divisors of n , $q_d(n)$ denotes the product of all proper divisors of n . In this paper, we study the properties of the sequences $\{p_d(n)\}$ and $\{q_d(n)\}$, and prove that the Makowski & Schinzel conjecture hold for the sequences $\{p_d(n)\}$ and $\{q_d(n)\}$.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let n be a positive integer, $p_d(n)$ denotes the product of all positive divisors of n . That is, $p_d(n) = \prod_{d|n} d$. For example, $p_d(1) = 1$, $p_d(2) = 2$, $p_d(3) = 3$, $p_d(4) = 8$, $p_d(5) = 5$, $p_d(6) = 36$, \dots , $p_d(p) = p$, \dots . $q_d(n)$ denotes the product of all proper divisors of n . That is, $q_d(n) = \prod_{d|n, d < n} d$. For example, $q_d(1) = 1$, $q_d(2) = 1$, $q_d(3) = 1$, $q_d(4) = 2$, $q_d(5) = 1$, $q_d(6) = 6$, \dots . In problem 25 and 26 of [1], Professor F.Smarandach asked us to study the properties of the sequences $\{p_d(n)\}$ and $\{q_d(n)\}$. About this problem, it seems that none had studied it, at least we have not seen such a paper before. In this paper, we use the elementary methods to study the properties of the sequences $\{p_d(n)\}$ and $\{q_d(n)\}$, and prove that the Makowski & Schinzel conjecture hold for $p_d(n)$ and $q_d(n)$. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem 1. *For any positive integer n , we have the inequality*

$$\sigma(\phi(p_d(n))) \geq \frac{1}{2}p_d(n),$$

where $\phi(k)$ is the Euler's function and $\sigma(k)$ is the divisor sum function.

Theorem 2. *For any positive integer n , we have the inequality*

$$\sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) \geq \frac{1}{2}q_d(n).$$

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2. SOME LEMMAS

To complete the proof of the Theorems, we need the following two Lemmas:

Lemma 1. *For any positive integer n , we have the identities*

$$p_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad q_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}-1},$$

where $d(n) = \sum_{d|n} 1$ is the divisor function.

Proof. From the definition of $p_d(n)$ we know that

$$p_d(n) = \prod_{d|n} d = \prod_{d|n} \frac{n}{d}.$$

So by this formula we have

$$(1) \quad p_d^2(n) = \prod_{d|n} n = n^{d(n)}.$$

From (1) we immediately get

$$p_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}}$$

and

$$q_d(n) = \prod_{d|n, d < n} d = \frac{\prod_{d|n} d}{n} = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}-1}.$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 1.

Lemma 2. *For any positive integer n , let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ with $\alpha_i \geq 2$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, s$), p_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, s$) are some different primes with $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_s$, then we have the estimate*

$$\sigma(\phi(n)) \geq \frac{6}{\pi^2} n.$$

Proof. From the properties of the Euler's function we have

$$(2) \quad \begin{aligned} \phi(n) &= \phi(p_1^{\alpha_1}) \phi(p_2^{\alpha_2}) \cdots \phi(p_s^{\alpha_s}) \\ &= p_1^{\alpha_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2-1} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s-1} (p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) \cdots (p_s - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Let $(p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) \cdots (p_s - 1) = p_1^{\beta_1} p_2^{\beta_2} \cdots p_s^{\beta_s} q_1^{r_1} q_2^{r_2} \cdots q_t^{r_t}$, where $\beta_i \geq 0$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, s$, $r_j \geq 1$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, t$ and $q_1 < q_2 < \cdots < q_t$ are different primes. Then

from (2) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma(\phi(n)) &= \sigma(p_1^{\alpha_1+\beta_1-1} p_2^{\alpha_2+\beta_2-1} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s+\beta_s-1} q_1^{r_1} q_2^{r_2} \dots q_t^{r_t}) \\
&= \prod_{i=1}^s \frac{p_i^{\alpha_i+\beta_i} - 1}{p_i - 1} \prod_{j=1}^t \frac{q_j^{r_j+1} - 1}{q_j - 1} \\
&= p_1^{\alpha_1+\beta_1} p_2^{\alpha_2+\beta_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s+\beta_s} q_1^{r_1} q_2^{r_2} \dots q_t^{r_t} \prod_{i=1}^s \frac{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{\alpha_i+\beta_i}}}{p_i - 1} \prod_{j=1}^t \frac{1 - \frac{1}{q_j^{r_j+1}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q_j}} \\
&= n \prod_{i=1}^s \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{\alpha_i+\beta_i}}\right) \prod_{j=1}^t \frac{1 - \frac{1}{q_j^{r_j+1}}}{1 - \frac{1}{q_j}} \\
&= n \prod_{i=1}^s \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{\alpha_i+\beta_i}}\right) \prod_{j=1}^t \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j} + \dots + \frac{1}{q_j^{r_j}}\right) \\
&\geq n \prod_{i=1}^s \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{\alpha_i+\beta_i}}\right) \\
&\geq n \prod_{i=1}^s \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^2}\right) \\
&\geq n \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Noticing $\prod_p \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p^2}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = \zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, we immediately get

$$\sigma(\phi(n)) \geq n \cdot \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2}\right) = \frac{6}{\pi^2} n.$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 2.

3. PROOF OF THE THEOREMS

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the Theorems. First we prove Theorem 1. We separate n into prime and composite number two cases. If n is a prime, then $d(n) = 2$. This time by Lemma 1 we have

$$p_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}} = n.$$

Hence, from this formula and $\phi(n) = n - 1$ we immediately get

$$\sigma(\phi(p_d(n))) = \sigma(n - 1) = \sum_{d|n-1} d \geq n - 1 \geq \frac{n}{2} = \frac{1}{2} p_d(n).$$

If n is a composite number, then $d(n) \geq 3$. If $d(n) = 3$, we have $n = p^2$, where p is a prime. So that

$$(3) \quad p_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}} = p^{d(n)} = p^3.$$

From Lemma 2 and (3) we can easily get the inequality

$$\sigma(\phi(p_d(n))) = \sigma(\phi(p^3)) \geq \frac{6}{\pi^2} p^3 \geq \frac{1}{2} p_d(n).$$

If $d(n) \geq 4$, let $p_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}} = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ with $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_s$, then we have $\alpha_i \geq 2, i = 1, 2, \cdots, s$. So from Lemma 2 we immediately obtain the inequality

$$\sigma(\phi(p_d(n))) \geq \frac{6}{\pi^2} p_d(n) \geq \frac{1}{2} p_d(n).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.

The proof of Theorem 2. We also separate n into two cases. If n is a prime, then we have

$$q_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}-1} = 1.$$

From this formula we have

$$\sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) = 1 \geq \frac{1}{2} q_d(n).$$

If n is a composite number, we have $d(n) \geq 3$, then we discuss the following four cases. First, if $d(n) = 3$, then $n = p^2$, where p is a prime. So we have

$$q_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}-1} = p^{d(n)-2} = p.$$

From this formula and the proof of Theorem 1 we easily get

$$\sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) \geq \frac{1}{2} q_d(n).$$

Second, if $d(n) = 4$, from Lemma 1 we may get

$$(4) \quad q_d(n) = n^{\frac{d(n)}{2}-1} = n$$

and $n = p^3$ or $n = p_1 p_2$, where p, p_1 and p_2 are primes with $p_1 < p_2$. If $n = p^3$, from (4) and Lemma 2 we have

$$(5) \quad \begin{aligned} \sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) &= \sigma(\phi(n)) = \sigma(\phi(p^3)) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} p^3 = \frac{1}{2} q_d(n). \end{aligned}$$

If $n = p_1 p_2$, we consider $p_1 = 2$ and $p_1 > 2$ two cases. If $2 = p_1 < p_2$, then $p_2 - 1$ is an even number. Supposing $p_2 - 1 = p_1^{\beta_1} p_2^{\beta_2} q_1^{r_1} \cdots q_t^{r_t}$ with $q_1 < q_2 < \cdots < q_t$.

$q_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, t)$ are different primes and $r_j \geq 1 (j = 1, 2, \dots, t)$, $\beta_1 \geq 1, \beta_2 \geq 0$. Note that the proof of Lemma 2 and (4) we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) &= \sigma(\phi(n)) \\
 &= n \prod_{i=1}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{1+\beta_i}}\right) \prod_{j=1}^t \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j} + \dots + \frac{1}{q_j^{r_j}}\right) \\
 &\geq n \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2}\right) \\
 &\geq n \left(1 - \frac{1}{4}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{3}\right) \\
 (6) \qquad &= \frac{1}{2} q_d(n).
 \end{aligned}$$

If $2 < p_1 < p_2$, then both $p_1 - 1$ and $p_2 - 1$ are even numbers. Let $(p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) = p_1^{\beta_1} p_2^{\beta_2} q_1^{r_1} q_2^{r_2} \dots q_t^{r_t}$ with $q_1 < q_2 < \dots < q_t$, $q_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, t)$ are different primes and $r_j \geq 1 (j = 1, 2, \dots, t)$, $\beta_1, \beta_2 \geq 0$, then we have $q_1 = 2$ and $r_1 \geq 2$. So from the proof of Lemma 2 and (4) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) &= \sigma(\phi(n)) \\
 &= n \prod_{i=1}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{1+\beta_i}}\right) \prod_{j=1}^t \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_j} + \dots + \frac{1}{q_j^{r_j}}\right) \\
 &\geq n \prod_{i=1}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2}\right) \\
 &\geq n \prod_{i=1}^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{3}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{5}\right) \\
 &\geq n \prod_{i=1}^2 \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i}\right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i}\right)\right] \\
 &\geq n \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2}\right) \\
 &\geq n \frac{6}{\pi^2} \\
 (7) \qquad &\geq \frac{1}{2} q_d(n).
 \end{aligned}$$

Combining (5), (6) and (7) we obtain

$$\sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) \geq \frac{1}{2} q_d(n) \quad \text{if } d(n) = 4.$$

Third, if $d(n) = 5$, we have $n = p^4$, where p is a prime. Then from Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 we immediately get

$$\sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) = \sigma(\phi(p^6)) \geq \frac{6}{\pi^2} p^6 = \frac{1}{2} q_d(n).$$

Finally, if $d(n) \geq 6$, then from Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 we can easily obtain

$$\sigma(\phi(q_d(n))) \geq \frac{1}{2}q_d(n).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

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